

Modeling evacuation activities amid compound hazards: Insights from hurricane Irma in Southeast Florida

Yu Han^{a,*}, Wei Zhai^b, Pallab Mozumder^c, Cees van Westen^a, Changjie Chen^d

^a University of Twente, Faculty of Geo-Information Science and Earth Observation (ITC), Enschede, Netherlands

^b School of Architecture and Planning, University of Texas at San Antonio, San Antonio, USA

^c Department of Economics, Florida International University, Miami, FL 33199, USA

^d Florida Institute for Built Environment Resilience, University of Florida, FL, USA

ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Hurricane Evacuation
Agent-Based Modeling
MATSim
Compound hazards

ABSTRACT

Given the destructive nature of hurricanes in tropical regions, pre-disaster evacuation has emerged as a critical approach for hurricane preparedness. Nevertheless, the compounding effects of natural hazards and the outbreak of infectious diseases, such as Covid-19, significantly challenge hurricane evacuation management. To investigate emergency responses under compound hazards, this study develops an activity-based model to measure the evacuation behaviors of individuals, using Hurricane Irma as a case study. Four scenarios are designed, including a single hurricane hazard, Hurricane Irma compounded with a pandemic like Covid-19, Hurricane Irma compounded with flood damage to the transportation network, and a combination of all these hazards. The metropolis-hasting algorithm is utilized to generate a population with socioeconomic attributes, which is then allocated to census block groups covering Palm Beach, Broward, Miami-Dade, and Monroe Counties in Florida. Datasets from multiple sources are used to measure evacuation decisions, which are subsequently simulated using MATSim. The results highlight the potential impacts of compound hazards on transportation systems, including increased congestions in scenarios involving compounded hurricanes and floods, especially between 10 a.m. and 7p.m. Moreover, a higher proportion of socially vulnerable populations is observed in scenarios involving compounded hurricanes and pandemics, particularly in the Key West area. The developed model could be further applied to measure the indirect impacts of natural hazards on transportation systems.

1. Introduction

Hurricanes are among the most destructive natural hazards affecting coastal communities. They cause extensive damage to infrastructures and loss of life through intense rainfall, storm surges, and powerful winds. The 2017 Atlantic hurricane season, with three catastrophic events, including Hurricanes Harvey, Irma, and Maria, caused significant population displacement, billions of dollars in direct damages, and further indirect losses due to disrupted access to essential services (Long et al., 2020; West, 2023). The frequent occurrence of such severe events has made evacuation a crucial strategy for hazard mitigation and preparedness in coastal areas (Huang et al., 2021). Nevertheless, large-scale evacuations, often involving millions of people and vehicles moving across extensive transportation networks, pose substantial challenges for emergency management (Lindell et al., 2018).

Although considerable efforts have been devoted to evacuation planning and management, effectively managing hurricane evacuation remains challenging in the context of emerging compound hazards – situations where two or more hazardous events interact, creating complex and combined effects that are more severe than the impact of any single hazard occurring alone. The unpredictable nature and complex interactions of these compound hazards, exacerbated by climate change and ongoing urban development, expose growing populations to more frequent, intensified, and prolonged hazardous events (AghaKouchak et al., 2020). Consequently, efficient evacuation management would be imperative for enhancing community resilience.

Identifying vulnerable areas and understanding the accessibility of socially vulnerable populations are crucial steps in mitigating hurricane threats (Kutela et al., 2023). For example, several studies have used composite vulnerability scores to assess transit-dependent populations

* Corresponding author at: Faculty of Geo-information Science and Earth Observation (ITC), University of Twente, Room 1419, Langezijds, PO Box 217, 7500 AE Enschede, The Netherlands.

E-mail address: hanyu.bit@gmail.com (Y. Han).

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2024.100933>

Received 31 October 2023; Received in revised form 29 August 2024; Accepted 17 October 2024

Available online 23 October 2024

2214-367X/© 2024 The Author(s). Published by Elsevier Ltd on behalf of Hong Kong Society for Transportation Studies. This is an open access article under the CC BY license (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/>).

in hurricane-prone areas (Bian & Wilmot, 2017) and leveraged data from social media and mobile phone to estimate population at risk and track migration after Hurricane Maria in Puerto Rico (Acosta et al., 2020). Zhu et al. (2020) further measured road network accessibility during hurricane evacuation under dynamic road demands and hurricane characteristics, focusing on estimated route choices across Florida.

Beyond social vulnerability analysis, research on hurricane evacuation has primarily dealt with the demographic and socioeconomic factors influencing individuals' decisions to evacuate (Lindell, 2008; Pan, 2020). For example, Goldberg et al. (2020) applied a Meta-Cognitive model using survey data, demonstrating that future hurricane evacuation decisions are strongly influenced by past evacuation behaviors and the degree of confidence in their past behaviors. Existing studies have identified various factors, such as demographic and socioeconomic characteristics of evacuees, local evacuation order, as well as peer effects, influence individuals' evacuation behaviors (Huang et al., 2012; Jiang et al., 2023). Yang et al. (2019) developed an Agent-Based Model (ABM) to capture diffusion of households' hurricane evacuation decisions on the spatial and temporal scales relying on their home-work social networks under the evacuation order. Harris et al. (2022) presented an integrated a hurricane-forecast-evacuation model to evaluate human evacuation decision-making and interactions between them during Hurricane Irma. Brower et al. (2023) developed an ABM to measure the evacuation behaviors and emergency department (ED) visits of the population during Hurricane Harvey relying on evacuation data from smartphone locations (Long et al., 2020) and daily ED visit. Kutela et al. (2023) applied regression analysis and text mining for public survey data after Hurricane Irma and found traffic conditions, evacuation orders, previous hurricane experience, the existence of public shelters, household income, and gasoline availability are significantly associated with evacuation decisions. Jiang et al. (2023) conducted an empirical analysis to measure evacuation decisions and expenditures under different hurricane evacuation orders. They found evacuation orders and past hurricane evacuation experiences positively contribute to evacuation decisions, and the probability of evacuation decreases as the increase of expected evacuation cost.

Public shelters provide a safe refuge for individuals during extreme weather conditions and are crucial component in evacuation management. Research in this area focuses on optimizing shelter locations for improved accessibility, operational effectiveness during disasters, and the decision-making process of individuals to evacuate to public shelters. Models such as those proposed by Li et al. (2012) optimized shelter locations in North Carolina by minimizing travel costs while considering household route choices. Additionally, studies like those presented by Wong et al. (2020) explored the complexities of shelter management for special needs populations and analyzed the factors influencing individuals' decisions to use public shelters.

Computer-based simulation models have served for decades to evaluate traffic patterns, control strategies, and emerging travel demands on the transportation systems, and have been increasingly used in hurricane evacuation planning (Boyce & Williams, 2015; Lindell et al., 2018). Feng and Lin (2021) developed a macro-level hurricane evacuation model based on traffic demand and user equilibrium to reproduce spatial temporal evolution of traffic flows during Hurricane Irma in Florida. In contrast to macro-level transportation optimization models, micro-level simulation models, which focus on individual travel decisions, provide detailed insights into evacuation behaviors and can capture human responses to evacuation policies (Lindell et al., 2018). For example, Onelcin et al. (2013) simulated evacuation behaviors in case of chemical accidents with both a mesoscopic simulation tool, Cube Avenue, and microscopic simulation software, MATSim. Their results show that interactions among different individuals in the Cube Avenue are still on aggregated level. Yamada and Yamasaki (2021) developed an agent-based model to simulate tsunami evacuation in Japan by comparing two evacuation strategies: evacuate to the nearest shelter versus evacuate to inland shelters. Their findings highlighted the

importance to consider the direction of the coastline in tsunami evacuation planning.

The unprecedented combination of climate hazards with public health crises, such as the COVID-19 pandemic, has introduced new complexities to the evacuation management. Disaster damages on the transportation system during and after natural hazards could disrupt essential services and decrease the functionality of the transportation network. Amini and Padgett (2023) developed a probabilistic framework to evaluate debris damage of hurricanes on transportation infrastructures. The model results indicated probabilistic risk of transportation infrastructure and connectivity loss ratio to emergency medical center facing hurricane hazards in a case study area of Galveston Island, TX. Han et al. (2022) utilized an activity-based travel demand model to access the effects of storm surge, sea level rise, and population growth on households' travel activities in Florida. Their results highlighted traffic disruptions caused by damages on the transportation system and the significance of implementing adaptation measures. The outbreak of Covid-19 pandemic coupled with climate hazards has revealed the exacerbated risk of compound hazards (Phillips et al., 2020; Zaitchik et al., 2022). Dargin et al. (2021) assessed compound hazard risk using human movement data, Covid-19 cases, and the social vulnerability index. They found that increased contact in high-risk areas during hurricane preparations and disruptions of healthcare services due to disaster damage could elevate the transmission risk of Covid-19 in coastal communities during hurricane seasons.

While much research has focused on evacuation under single hazard scenarios, there is an increasing recognition of the need to address evacuation management in the context of multiple, interacting hazards (Tilloy et al., 2019). Compound hazards, such as the combination of storm surges, heavy rainfall, and infectious diseases, present challenges that have not been widely explored in evacuation modeling (Moftakhari et al., 2017; Zscheischler et al., 2018). For example, Collins et al. (2021) collected survey for residents in Florida and found significant number of individuals were unwilling to evacuate to public shelters during the Covid-19 pandemic. Nevertheless, changes in household evacuation plan under this circumstance could increase risk during a mandatory evacuation order, particularly due to storm surge and other hurricane-related hazards impacting the transportation system.

As climate change leads to more rapidly intensifying hurricanes and increases the frequency of compound hazards, it becomes increasingly crucial to understand and manage evacuation activities in these scenarios. This study aims to fill this gap by examining evacuation behaviors amid compound hazards, using Hurricane Irma in 2017 as a case study. Utilizing the activity-based travel demand model MATSim, we simulate individuals' evacuation behaviors in Southeast Florida, providing new insights into the complexities of evacuation management under compound hazards.

2. Methodology

2.1. Study area and data collection

Southeast Florida is a coastal metropolitan region located in the southeastern of the US and comprises three most populated counties in Florida, namely Broward County, Miami-Dade County, and Palm Beach County (U.S. Census Bureau, 2024). It is also one of the most vulnerable regions in the US to coastal hazards, experienced more than 49 hurricanes in history (Emrich et al., 2017). In September 2017, Hurricane Irma, an extremely powerful Category 5 hurricane that originated near Cape Verde, made landfall in southwest Florida and caused catastrophic damages, as illustrated in the upper left of Fig. 1. Hurricane Irma was the most powerful Atlantic Ocean hurricane in the recorded history. Millions of residents in Florida evacuated their home. Mandatory evacuation orders were issued in 54 of 67 counties in Florida (Anand et al., 2024). Fig. 1 shows the pathway of Hurricane Irma, locations of the study area, and the exposed population in census block groups. Our

Fig. 1. Hurricane Irma path and location of the study area.

study area includes four counties, including Palm Beach, Broward, Miami-Dade, and Monroe Counties. The left part of Fig. 1 shows that counties in the south and west of Florida, such as Monroe, were on the path center of Hurricane Irma. Although the three most populated counties in the Southeast Florida were not on the hurricane path center, they all experienced serious impacts from Irma, primarily due to massive pre-disaster evacuation. Fig. 1 also shows the study area with the population distributed in census blocks and the distribution of shelter locations. Most population in this region are distributed along the east coast. The distribution of shelters is also more centered around areas with high population density.

Datasets were collected from multiple sources. First, a hurricane evacuation survey was conducted for hurricane Irma affected areas in South Florida between August and December of 2020 to measure factors that influence individuals' evacuation decisions for Hurricane Irma and for the compound hazard situation amid an assumed pandemic like Covid-19 (Mojumder et al., 2022). Second, the Southeast Florida Household Travel (SFHT) survey, which was conducted between 2014 and 2017 by Transportation Planning Organizations in Broward County, Miami-Dade County, and Palm Beach County and Florida Department of Transportation (FDOT), was used to generate population synthesis in the study area. The dataset covers travel patterns, home, and work locations observed over two entire years for 4172 individuals with diverse socioeconomic backgrounds. Since this dataset only covers the three counties, we also applied the census block groups data as ancillary data to reallocate the simulated population to the whole region that also covers Monroe County (see Section 2.3). Third, publicly available evacuation data, aggregated from smartphone locations during Hurricane Irma, was used to calibrate the developed evacuation decision model. The dataset was released by Long et al. (2020) and included individual evacuation status aggregated on census tract levels. Moreover, the transportation network data that covers the whole southeast Florida was obtained from the OpenStreetMap. To measure individuals' evacuation behaviors under the compound hurricane and storm surge flooding scenario, we used the flood inundation map of category 5 storm surge from the SLOSH model (Zachry et al., 2015). All datasets used in this research and their sources have been listed in Table 1.

Table 1
Data description and sources.

Dataset	Description	Sources
Hurricane Irma Evacuation Survey	Conducted between August 28, 2023 and December 22, 2023	The survey was designed by and conducted by survey company Qualtrics
Household Travel Survey	Individual and household travel characteristics covering the southeast Florida	FSUTMSOnline statewide and regional modeling data
Evacuation Data During Hurricane Irma	Individual evacuation status aggregated on census tract level	Long et al. (2020)
Transportation Network	Interconnected transportation network with road links and nodes	OpenStreetMap
Hurricane Shelter Locations	Locations of public shelters with capacity and policies	Florida Geographical Digital Library (FGDL)
ACS Census Block Group Data	Sociodemographic attributes in American Community Survey (ACS) census block groups	FGDL
Category 5 Storm Surge Flood Map	US Gulf and East Coast Category 5 Storm Surge Inundation from The SLOSH (Sea, Lake, and Overland Surges from Hurricanes) model	National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA)

2.2. Model framework

This study utilizes MATSim, an open-sourced activity-based multi-agent simulation tool, to simulate traffic on the transportation system. In MATSim, each traveler is represented as an individual agent. These simulated agents are anonymous entities, each capable of carrying out their daily activities independently. Initial travel demand on the transportation network is aggregated based on travel plans of these agents. During the simulation, agents' travel plans are scored after each iteration, with agents adapt their travel plans in response to traffic conditions, such as congestion at intersections and link capacities. The optimal travel plan of each agent is determined once model results converged.

To construct the simulation model in MATSim, three kinds of inputs are required: a transportation network file, a population file, and a configuration file. Fig. 2 illustrates the overall modeling framework. The

Fig. 2. Flowchart Illustrating the Model Development Process.

transportation network file represents an interconnected road network, comprising both road edges and nodes. Road edges contain information such as road capacity, post speed limits, and directions. The direction of a road edge is indicated by its starting and ending nodes, which are points that connect the road links. Traffic is typically generated at the starting node and then distributed across the transportation network. The original transportation network was obtained from OpenStreetMap using the OSMnx package (Boeing, 2017). By conducting a spatial join for the transportation network and flood map, we identified nodes and edges damaged by flooding and updated the transportation network.

The population file contains evacuation information for each agent in chronological order. To synthesize population with socio-demographical attributes and evacuation decisions, we combined household travel survey data, ACS census data at the block group level, Hurricane Irma evacuation survey data, and evacuation rates at the census tract level. We utilized Metropolis-Hasting algorithm, incorporating household travel survey data, to synthesize population. This synthesized population was then redistributed based on the census block group data, assuming a distribution for each socioeconomic attribute from their mean and standard deviation. To develop a hurricane evacuation decision model, we employed evacuation data from Hurricane Irma and calculated evacuation rates at the census tract level. We then utilized the synthesized population to generate their evacuation decisions. The population file includes key information such as whether a household evacuated, the time of evacuation, and origin-destination details.

Alongside the population file and the transportation network file, a model configuration file is used to specify crucial model parameters that significantly influence model results. These parameters include the number of model iteration, storage capacity, and flow capacity parameter, among others. In our model, the statistics converged after 50 iterations. Based on the proportional of the simulated population to the total population in the region, we selected a flow capacity parameter 0.2 and storage capacity factor 0.3 (Horni et al., 2016). All MATSim input and output files are stored in the extensible marked language (xml) format before and after model simulation.

2.3. Population simulation

We developed the Markov Chain Monte Carlo (MCMC) method to generate population and then redistributed the generated population to the whole study area using census data. More specifically, the Metropolis-Hasting (MH) algorithm was applied to the household travel survey in population synthesis. We generated 80,000 agents in the simulation, which corresponds to about 5% households in the study area. Different from other Bayesian approaches, which needs to know the conditional distributions of variables and iteratively sample one variable at a time (Han et al., 2022; Saadi et al., 2016), the MH algorithm aims to simulate a sample of population attributes relying on the full joint proposal distribution with an acceptance ratio.

The MH algorithm starts with an initial population sample $\pi(x)$ derived from the travel survey data, which contains an individual's socioeconomic attributes. We then generated a new candidate sample x' from a proposal distribution $q(x'|x_t)$, where x_t is the current sample at iteration t . The proposal distribution is usually defined by swapping or altering attribute values from the survey data. In our simulation, a candidate sample will be generated from the joint proposal distribution based on the sample data. After generated the new candidate sample, an acceptance ratio α is calculated to determine if the new sample x' should be accepted or rejected. The acceptance ratio is calculated using the following equation.

$$\alpha = \min\left(1, \frac{\pi(x') \bullet q(x_t|x')}{\pi(x_t) \bullet q(x'|x_t)}\right) \quad (1)$$

In Equation (1), $\pi(x')$ represents the probability of the target distribution for the new sample, and $\pi(x_t)$ represents the probability in the target distribution for the current sample. $q(x_t|x')$ and $q(x'|x_t)$ are conditional probabilities from the proposal distribution for x_t and x' , respectively. They describe how likely it is to move from one state to another in the MH process. For our simulation, we assume swapping the attributes between two individual samples in the population data is symmetric, thus $q(x_t|x') = q(x'|x_t)$. Therefore, the calculation of α is simplified to compare the likelihood of the new sample to the current sample. If the acceptance ratio is greater or equal to a random value from a uniform distribution $U(0, 1)$, then the proposed states will be accepted, otherwise, the current states will remain unchanged. Using the

MH algorithm, we generated representative households and their corresponding attributes with a high degree of accuracy and flexibility. These attributes include number of vehicles in a household, family income, household head’s age, educational level, and race.

While the simulated population accurately reflects population characteristics observed in the travel survey, it does not fully capture local sociodemographic variations of the whole study area at the spatial scale. To address this, we then employed Bayesian inference approach to allocate individuals randomly across census block groups. This approach can be formulized as follows: we assumed a uniform distribution as the prior probability for the distribution of individuals within each census block group. We then calculated the likelihood function as the probability of observing the individual’s attributes, given that the individual belongs to a specific census tract. For continuous variables, we assumed a normal distribution with a coefficient of variation of 0.5, and for discrete attributes, we assumed a categorical distribution. We calculated the likelihoods as the product of probability densities, as shown in Equation (3).

$$p(A|T) = \prod_{i=1}^n P(A_i|T) \tag{2}$$

In Equation (3), A_i is the i -th attribute of the individual A , and n is the number of attributes considered. We calculated posterior probabilities of individuals within each census block group and weighted these posterior probabilities. Subsequently, we randomly allocated individuals to census tracts based on the weighted posterior probabilities.

2.4. Evacuation decisions of households

We utilized the Hurricane Irma evacuation survey data to estimate household evacuation decisions, focusing on whether they will evacuate, as well as when and where they would evacuate. Each household in the transportation network is represented as an individual evacuee. We applied the stepwise logistic model and identified significant predictors of evacuation decisions, including household income, the age and educational level of the household head, the neighborhood impact, and whether the household living in a flood zone, as illustrated in Table 2. We excluded factors such as ethnicity, home preparedness, special needs during evacuation, and the influence of friends and coworkers. Although these factors are relevant, they showed less significance in our logistic model. Since we assumed a single-day evacuation activity following the release of the evacuation order, we excluded the evacuation order as a significant factor influencing in the logistic model. For the analysis, we transformed continuous variables, such as age and family income, into categorical values. Since evacuation order is usually issued to evacuation zones, we measured neighborhood impact by calculating the average distance of each evacuation zone to the hurricane center path and normalized the values between 0 and 1.

When an agent decides to evacuate, they will then decide destination and evacuation time. There are three kinds of evacuation destinations, which are friends’ home, public shelter, or away from home. For evacuation to friends’ home and away from home, we randomly generated a destination outside of the hurricane affected area, and for the public shelter, we chose the nearest public shelter for the evacuee. In the survey

data, 104 over the 780 samples chosen public shelters as their evacuation destinations. We employed a stepwise logistic model to measure whether an evacuee would evacuate to public shelters. Table 2 show that variables include the age and educational level of a household head and whether the household living in a flood zone are statistically significant factors to predict evacuation decisions to public shelters. We randomly selected public shelters as evacuation destination for these households. For destinations other than public shelters, we randomly generated locations and randomly chose transportation nodes outside the study area and beyond the regions affected by Hurricane Irma. To estimate evacuation times for each evacuee, we used datasets from Long et al. (2020) to calculate evacuation rates and derive a probability distribution of evacuation times for each census tract. These distributions were then used to randomly generate evacuation times for each evacuee in the simulation.

2.5. Road network preparation

The Python package OSMnx was used to download transportation network data in the whole study region (Boeing, 2017). The downloaded dataset includes both transportation nodes and edges. To measure the impacts of flood damage on the transportation network, we applied the Category 5 storm surge inundation map from the SLOSH model. We assumed that local stormwater facilities for storm surge mitigation is designed for flood with the 50-year return period, which is equivalent to the peak surging height 3.57 m (FDOT, 2024b). We overlaid flood map onto the transportation network to identify damaged road links. We then removed inundated transport nodes and isolated road links, updating the network by keeping accessible nodes.

2.6. Model simulation and validation

The MATSim model was constructed and simulated using IntelliJ IDEA. We carefully examined model input files, including population and network files for each scenario. The validation of the model results was carried out through a two-step process. First, we divided the simulated population file into training and test sets and compared the model-generated results. We compared conditional probabilities of attributes between the simulated data and the test sets. Second, we validated the simulated model results by comparing them with observed evacuation data from Long et al. (2020) to validate simulation results in the base model.

2.7. Evacuation scenarios

We developed four scenarios to access the impacts of compound hazards on the transportation system. To compare impacts of compound hazards, we maintained the same model parameters in the configuration file. Instead, we adjusted the model input files for the population and network to reflect the different scenarios. Scenario 1 serves as the base scenario, simulating one day of evacuation activities on the transportation network following the release of the evacuation order and before the landfall of Hurricane Irma. In this scenario, the evacuation

Table 2
Evacuation decision models from the evacuation survey data.

	Whether an individual will evacuate				Whether evacuate to a public shelter			
	Estimate	Std. Error	Z-value	Pr (> z)	Estimate	Std. Error	Z-value	Pr (> z)
Intercept	-1.829	1.226	-1.491	0.136	0.682	0.375	1.82	0.07 (.)
Income level	0.056	0.0448	1.24	0.215	-	-	-	-
Age category	-0.982	0.489	-2.009	4.45e-2 (*)	-0.345	0.167	-2.07	0.04 (*)
Education level	0.546	0.177	3.086	2e-3 (**)	0.069	0.035	1.99	0.05 (*)
Neighborhood influence	0.432	0.112	3.853	1.2e-4 (***)	-	-	-	-
Living in flood zone	1.697	0.313	5.429	5.6e-8 (***)	0.252	0.073	3.43	7.8e-4 (***)

Notes: *p < 0.1; **p < 0.05; ***p < 0.01.

decision model is built based on the multi-sourced datasets. We constructed evacuation activities for each agent and then used it as model inputs. Scenario 2 represents a compound hazard scenario that Hurricane Irma makes landfall in South Florida coinciding the pandemic like Covid-19. This scenario models the compounding impact of hurricane and the pandemic on evacuation behaviors. In our simulation, the socially vulnerable population will not evacuate, while other evacuees will evacuate to communities unaffected by the hurricane, such as hotels or the homes of friends or relatives outside Hurricane Irma’s impact zone. This scenario highlights public health concerns during evacuation under compound hazards. Scenario 3 models the compound effects of a hurricane and flooding. Prior to Hurricane Irma’s landfall, strong winds and storm surges are predicted to cause flood damages on the transportation network. The model measures flood inundation and adjusted the travel speed based on a nonlinear relationship between the safety travel speed and flood inundation according to [Pregnolato et al. \(2016\)](#). This scenario highlights the interdependence between hurricanes and storm surge flooding, where flood damage to the transportation system directly affects evacuation efficiency. Scenario 4 combines the effects of the pandemic and storm surge damage outlined in Scenario 2 and Scenario 3. It simulates the compound impacts of a Covid-19-like pandemic and flood damage from Hurricane Irma on the transportation system during evacuation. In this scenario, the compound hazards could trigger cascading effects, including reduced evacuation of socially vulnerable populations due to pandemic concerns and increased traffic on the transportation network caused by storm surge flooding. The interaction between these hazards could create evacuation challenges and heighten social vulnerability during the evacuation process. In the four designed scenarios, only individuals who decide to evacuate will initiate their evacuation activities. Those who choose not to evacuate will remain at home throughout the simulation.

3. Results

The population was synthesized using the Metropolis-Hasting algorithm. To ensure synthesized samples from Markov chain accurately represent the target distributions from the travel survey data, we examined the mean values of the generated population attributes. [Fig. 3](#)

shows mean values of selected attributes in the simulation process. Among the total of 80,000 simulated population, the mean values of attributes such as the number of vehicles per household, agents’ age category, educational level, and family income category all converged after generating 20,000 samples. [Fig. 4](#) compares the conditional probabilities of two attributes between the simulated data and the travel survey data. The x-axis represents the conditional probabilities between two attributes in the travel survey data, while the y-axis shows the corresponding conditional probabilities in the simulated population data. Although a few conditional probabilities slightly deviated from the fitted line, the simulated results generally reflect the conditional relationships observed in the original data.

After generating the population for our study area, we randomly distributed the generated population across census block groups and associated each household head with a transport node within the census block group. As detailed in [Section 2.3](#), population distribution to census blocks involved calculating the population likelihood for each block and then randomly assigning individuals based on these likelihoods. [Fig. 5](#) presents the aggregated results across census blocks for total population and median household income. The results reveal a strong positive linear relationship between the survey data and our simulated population data for these two variables. Nevertheless, we noticed some discrepancies in certain census blocks, where the simulated data slightly deviates from the survey findings. For other attributes, our allocated population showed positive correlations as well but the linear trends between simulated data and actual were less significant. Specifically, the correlation for the percentage of the age population is 0.83, but for education levels, it is only 0.33. This result is due to that the travel survey data only covers a limited sample size and could not fully capture the sociodemographic statistics of the population in our study area.

We then modeled the evacuation decisions of the population and simulated their activities on the transportation network. [Fig. 6](#) compares the time-of-day trip distributions for the simulated evacuation and the actual evacuation data from the mobile phone records by [Long et al. \(2020\)](#). Our simulated time-of-day evacuation activities align closely with the actual evacuation patterns. The results show an increase in evacuation activities starting after 5 am, with a gradually peak occurring after 10 am. Afterward, the traffic on the transportation network

Fig. 3. Mean Values of Attributes for Simulated Population using MCMC Algorithm.

Fig. 4. The comparison of conditional probabilities of attributes between simulated data and the SFL travel survey data.

Fig. 5. Comparison between actual and simulated population (A) and household income (B) in Census Tracts.

diminishes after 8 pm.

We categorized evacuation start times into five groups based on the SFL travel survey: Early AM (12 am to 6 am), Morning (6 am to 10 am), Midday (10 am to 3 pm), Early PM (3 pm to 7 pm), and Evening (7 pm to 12 am), as shown in Fig. 7. The results show travel time distributions across different time periods for each scenario. It was observed that evacuation activities initiated in the evening have the shortest average travel times. Moreover, evacuation that began in the early morning and early evening periods generally experienced shorter travel times. The travel time distribution for the early evening period exhibited a bimodal pattern, likely due to the varied destination preferences of evacuees. Except for these instances, travel time distributions during other periods displayed a pronounced long-tail feature. This result highlighted increased congestions from the Morning through to the Early PM.

It is also observed that travel times in the Early AM were longer in Scenarios 1 and 3 compared to those in Scenario 2 and 4. Similarly,

Fig. 8 delineates the distributions of trip volume over a 24-hour period across different time categories in the four scenarios. The overall patterns of trip volume distribution throughout the day were consistent across all scenarios. The only difference is that Scenarios 1 and 2 exhibited longer tails in their trip volume distributions compared to Scenario 3 and 4. Evacuation activities with travel times ranging from 480 to 600 min, as well as those longer than 600 min, had their peak travel time started around 10 AM and 2 PM. Activities with travel time between 240 and 480 min exhibited later peak start times, indicating increased congestion between 10 am and 4 pm. Conversely, for travel time under 240 min, departures were more uniformly distributed throughout the day, ranging from 8 am to 9 pm.

To assess traffic on the transportation network during evacuation, we analyzed the total number of trips on each road segment based on the simulated travel route for all evacuation activities, as show in Fig. 9. In terms of the number of evacuation trips, both Scenario 1 and Scenario 3

Fig. 6. Time of Day Evacuation Frequency Distributions for Actual and Simulated Data.

Fig. 7. Scenario-Based Travel Time Distributions in Different Evacuation Time Periods.

recorded 69714 trips each, whereas Scenario 2 and 4 each recorded 27860 evacuation trips. In general, roads experiencing high volume of evacuation trips were major planned evacuation routes, indicating their importance for evacuation. Notably, the roads connecting Key West to the mainland recorded the highest traffic volume, emphasizing its

critical role during the evacuation. In Scenario 2, the transportation network experienced a reduction in traffic due to fewer evacuees. Scenario 3 mirrored Scenario 1 in terms of travel activities, but experienced infrastructure damages due to hurricane storm surge. As a result, few trips were on some critical roads, especially the roads between Key West

Fig. 8. Scenario-Based Evacuation Time in Different Travel Time Categories.

Island and inland area. Scenario 4 observed a decrease in trip volume across the transportation system, with no traffic on the roads leading to Key West due to extensive road damages in that area. These results indicate varying impact levels associated with compound hazards.

We further show non-evacuated vulnerable population in each scenario at the census tracts level. Vulnerable populations were identified as individuals who are either over 65, belong to a minority group, or have a household income below \$35000. Results in Fig. 10 indicated that population in the southern region exhibit higher social vulnerability during evacuation, especially when facing a compound pandemic hazard like Covid-19 or transportation system damage. In Scenario 1 and 2, there was no damage to the transportation system, fewer vulnerable individuals remained in the Key West islands. However, due to the pandemic, the number of vulnerable individuals increased in the study area in Scenario 2 and 3. Scenario 4 showed that, under the compound effects of pandemic and transport infrastructure damages, an increase in vulnerable populations is observed in the Key West islands and east coast.

4. Conclusions

Forecasting human evacuation activities on the transportation system under compound hazards has important implications for emergency management. This study developed an activity-based travel demand model to simulate household evacuation behaviors under compound hazards scenarios using MATSim. We began by generating a synthetic population and redistributed the simulated population across census block groups using Bayesian approaches. The synthesized population

results indicated that our developed methodology effectively captured the population attributes in the study area. While the generated population data accurately reflected overall population and income distributions on the spatial scale, the linear correlations for age and educational levels were weaker on census block levels. This indicates limitations in the travel survey data, which could not fully represent socioeconomic characteristics of the whole study area. Additionally, the transportation network, constructed using open data, allowed us to include the Key West area, a region not considered in existing Florida Regional Transportation Models (FDOT, 2024a).

Using Hurricane Irma as a case study, we developed four compound scenarios to measure evacuation activities on the transportation system. Our results, aggregated based on individual evacuation behaviors, revealed that compound hazards, such as hurricane combined with flooding, could significantly increase congestions between 10 a.m. and 7p.m. Additionally, our findings showed that populations in the southern region, including Key West islands and the east coast, exhibit higher social vulnerability under compound hazards, particularly when facing the compounded hazards of a pandemic and transport infrastructure damage.

Given that climate change could result in more fast-intensifying hurricanes and compound hazards, it is crucial for emergency managers to consider the complex impacts of multi-hazards. The methodologies developed in this study can be further applied in other regions for managing both natural and man-made multi-hazard scenarios. For example, future studies can further integrate top-down microeconomic approaches and dynamic natural hazard modeling to measure the system-wide impacts of cascading hazards (Santos et al., 2023).

Fig. 9. Total Number of Trips on the Transportation Network under Four Evacuation Scenarios.

Simulating individual evacuation behaviors is a challenging task, as it involves complex travel decision-making of populations in emergency situations, including decisions on whether, when, and where to evacuate. Previous research has primarily focused on measuring hurricane evacuation volume in pre-disaster conditions or the evacuation decisions of individuals (Feng & Lin, 2021; Wong et al., 2020). This study provides an explicitly methodology to measure the spatial-temporal evacuation behaviors of individuals under compound hazard scenarios. Nonetheless, our study has limitations related to modeling evacuation behaviors for compound events and model uncertainty. First, this research utilized an evacuation survey to assess evacuation decisions of individuals under compound hazards, such as Hurricane Irma amidst pandemic like Covid-19 and flood damage scenarios. Nevertheless, the

developed logistic model could not effectively explain variations in human evacuation decisions across different compound hazard scenarios. Future studies could benefit from integrating dynamic hazard information to better capture individual’s evacuation decisions under complex situations. Second, the lack of accurate information on evacuation time and destinations could affect evacuation time estimation in simulation. We incorporated the census tract level evacuation data from Long et al. (2020) to enhance the developed evacuation decision model. For future research, large-scale, granular datasets on individual evacuation behaviors, combined with more advanced models, are needed to fully understand evacuation decisions, taking into account psychological, social, institutional, and economic factors (Zhao et al., 2022). Third, there are inherent uncertainties in the MATSim model. As noted by

Fig. 10. Total Non-evacuated Vulnerable Population Across Census Tracts under Four Evacuation Scenarios.

Bienzeisler et al. (2022), outputs from a MATSim model can vary even with constant model parameters. Moreover, due to simulating human activities are computational expensive, MATSim models are often scaled down, which can influence model accuracy. In this study, we relied on empirical values from existing studies to set up the simulation model (Horni et al., 2016). Future research should explore the sensitivity of parameter combinations on model results and better understand model uncertainties.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Yu Han: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Wei Zhai:** Writing – review & editing. **Pallab Mozumder:** Data curation. **Cees van Westen:** . **Changjie Chen:** Visualization.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This work was supported by the European Union's Horizon Europe Research and Innovation Program under Grant Agreement No 101073954.

References

- Acosta, R.J., Kishore, N., Irizarry, R.A., Buckee, C.O., 2020. Quantifying the dynamics of migration after Hurricane Maria in Puerto Rico. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 117 (51), 32772–32778. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.2001671117>.
- AghaKouchak, A., Chiang, F., Huning, L.S., Love, C.A., Mallakpour, I., Mazdiyasn, O., Moftakhari, H., Papalexioi, S.M., Ragno, E., Sadegh, M., 2020. Climate extremes and compound hazards in a warming world. *Annu. Rev. Earth Planet. Sci.* 48 (1), 519–548. <https://doi.org/10.1146/annurev-earth-071719-055228>.
- Amini, K., Padgett, J.E., 2023. Probabilistic risk assessment of hurricane-induced debris impacts on coastal transportation infrastructure. *Reliab. Eng. Syst. Saf.* 240, 109579. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.res.2023.109579>.
- Anand, H., Alemazkoo, N., Shafiee-Jood, M., 2024. HEvOD: A database of hurricane evacuation orders in the United States. *Sci. Data* 11 (1), 270. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41597-024-03100-x>.
- Bian, R., Wilmot, C.G., 2017. Measuring the vulnerability of disadvantaged populations during hurricane evacuation. *Nat. Hazards* 85 (2), 691–707. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11069-016-2598-0>.

- Bienzeisler, L., Lelke, T., Wage, O., Huck, L.-M., Friedrich, B., 2022. Uncertainty and variability analysis of agent-based transport models. *Transp. Res. Procedia* 62, 719–726. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trpro.2022.02.089>.
- Boeing, G., 2017. OSMnx: New methods for acquiring, constructing, analyzing, and visualizing complex street networks. *Comput. Environ. Urban Syst.* 65, 126–139. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2017.05.004>.
- Boyce, D.E., Williams, H.C.W.L., 2015. *Forecasting Urban Travel: Past, Present and Future*. Edward Elgar Publishing, 10.4337/9781784713591.
- Brower, A.E., Ramesh, B., Islam, K.A., Mortveit, H.S., Hoops, S., Vullikanti, A., Marathe, M.V., Zaitchik, B., Gohlke, J.M., Swarup, S., 2023. Augmenting the Social Vulnerability Index using an agent-based simulation of Hurricane Harvey. *Comput. Environ. Urban Syst.* 105, 102020. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2023.102020>.
- U.S. Census Bureau. (2024). *County Population Totals and Components of Change: 2020–2023*. Retrieved March 20, 2024 from <https://www.census.gov/data/tables/time-series/demo/popest/2020s-counties-total.html>.
- Collins, J., Polen, A., McSweeney, K., Colón-Burgos, D., Jernigan, I., 2021. Hurricane risk perceptions and evacuation decision-making in the age of COVID-19. *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* 102 (4), E836–E848. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-20-0229.1>.
- Dargin, J.S., Li, Q., Jawer, G., Xiao, X., Mostafavi, A., 2021. Compound hazards: An examination of how hurricane protective actions could increase transmission risk of COVID-19. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.* 65, 102560. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2021.102560>.
- Emrich, C.T., Morath, D.P., Bowser, G.C., Reeves, R., 2017. *Climate-Sensitive Hazards in Florida: Identifying and Prioritizing Threats to Build Resilience against Climate Effects. Hazards and Vulnerability Research Institute (HVRI), USA*.
- FDOT. (2024a). *FSUTMS - STATEWIDE AND REGIONAL MODELS*. Retrieved August 25, 2024 from https://www.fsutmsonline.net/index.php/model_pages/model_pages/.
- FDOT. (2024b). *Roadway Design Design Hurricane Surge Hydrographs*. Retrieved Apr 12, 2024 from <https://www.fdot.gov/roadway/drainage/dhsh.shtm>.
- Feng, K., Lin, N., 2021. Reconstructing and analyzing the traffic flow during evacuation in Hurricane Irma (2017). *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* 94, 102788. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2021.102788>.
- Goldberg, M.H., Marlon, J.R., Rosenthal, S.A., Leiserowitz, A., 2020. A meta-cognitive approach to predicting hurricane evacuation behavior. *Environ. Commun.* 14 (1), 6–12. <https://doi.org/10.1080/17524032.2019.1687100>.
- Han, Y., Chen, C., Peng, Z.-R., Mozumder, P., 2022. Evaluating impacts of coastal flooding on the transportation system using an activity-based travel demand model: a case study in Miami-Dade County, FL. *Transportation* 49 (1), 163–184. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11116-021-10172-w>.
- Harris, A., Roebber, P., Morss, R., 2022. An agent-based modeling framework for examining the dynamics of the hurricane-forecast-evacuation system. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.* 67, 102669. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2021.102669>.
- Horni, A., Nagel, K., Axhausen, K.W., 2016. *The Multi-Agent Transport Simulation MATSim*. Ubiquity Press. <http://www.jstor.org/stable/j.ctv3t5r7p>.
- Huang, S.-K., Lindell, M.K., Prater, C.S., Wu, H.-C., Siebeneck, L.K., 2012. Household evacuation decision making in response to hurricane Ike. *Nat. Hazard. Rev.* 13 (4), 283–296. [https://doi.org/10.1061/\(ASCE\)NH.1527-6996.0000074](https://doi.org/10.1061/(ASCE)NH.1527-6996.0000074).
- Huang, D., Wang, S., Liu, Z., 2021. A systematic review of prediction methods for emergency management. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.* 62, 102412. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2021.102412>.
- Jiang, F., Meng, S., Khan, M., Halim, N., Mozumder, P., 2023. Estimating willingness to pay and costs associated with hurricane evacuation. *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* 121, 103826. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2023.103826>.
- Kutela, B., Msechu, K.J., Kidando, E., Das, S., Kitali, A.E., 2023. Eliciting the influence of roadway and traffic conditions on hurricane evacuation decisions using regression-content analysis approach. *Travel Behav. Soc.* 33, 100623. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tbs.2023.100623>.
- Li, A.C.Y., Nozick, L., Xu, N., Davidson, R., 2012. Shelter location and transportation planning under hurricane conditions. *Transport. Res. Part e: Log. Transport. Rev.* 48 (4), 715–729. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tre.2011.12.004>.
- Lindell, M.K., 2008. EMBLEM2: An empirically based large scale evacuation time estimate model. *Transp. Res. A Policy Pract.* 42 (1), 140–154. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tra.2007.06.014>.
- Lindell, M.K., Murray-Tuite, P., Wolshon, B., Baker, J., 2018. *Large-Scale Evacuation: The Analysis, Modeling, and Management of Emergency Relocation from Hazardous Areas*. Taylor & Francis. <https://books.google.nl/books?id=-S.3DwAAQBAJ>.
- Long, E.F., Chen, M.K., Rohla, R., 2020. Political storms: Emergent partisan skepticism of hurricane risks. *Sci. Adv.* 6 (37), eabb7906. <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abb7906>.
- Moftakhari, H.R., Salvadori, G., AghaKouchak, A., Sanders, B.F., Matthew, R.A., 2017. Compounding effects of sea level rise and fluvial flooding. *Proc. Natl. Acad. Sci.* 114 (37), 9785–9790. <https://doi.org/10.1073/pnas.1620325114>.
- Mojumder, M. N. H., Sadri, A. M., Meng, S., Halim, N., & Mozumder, P. (2022). *Understanding Hurricane Evacuation Decision Consistency During a Pandemic: A Comparative Analysis Between Evacuation Scenarios of Hurricane Irma and COVID-19*.
- Onelcin, P., Mutlu, M.M., Alver, Y., 2013. Evacuation plan of an industrial zone: Case study of a chemical accident in Aliaga, Turkey and the comparison of two different simulation softwares. *Saf. Sci.* 60, 123–130. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssci.2013.07.006>.
- Pan, A., 2020. Study on the decision-making behavior of evacuation for coastal residents under typhoon storm surge disaster. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.* 45, 101522. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2020.101522>.
- Phillips, C.A., Caldas, A., Cleetus, R., Dahl, K.A., Declet-Barreto, J., Licker, R., Merner, L. D., Ortiz-Partida, J.P., Phelan, A.L., Spanger-Siegrfried, E., Talati, S., Trisos, C.H., Carlson, C.J., 2020. Compound climate risks in the COVID-19 pandemic. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 10 (7), 586–588. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-020-0804-2>.
- Pregolato, M., Ford, A., Robson, C., Glenis, V., Barr, S., Dawson, R., 2016. Assessing urban strategies for reducing the impacts of extreme weather on infrastructure networks. *R. Soc. Open Sci.* 3 (5), 160023. <https://doi.org/10.1098/rsos.160023>.
- Saadi, I., Teller, J., Cools, M., 2016. Belgium: the use of MATSim within an estimation framework for assessing economic impacts of river floods. In: Horni, A., Nagel, K., Axhausen, K.W. (Eds.), *The MultiAgent Transport Simulation MATSim*. Ubiquity Press, London, p. 399 <https://doi.org/10.5334/baw>.
- Santos, J., Roquel, K.I.D.Z., Lamberte, A., Tan, R.R., Aviso, K.B., Tapia, J.F.D., Solis, C.A., Yu, K.D.S., 2023. Assessing the economic ripple effects of critical infrastructure failures using the dynamic inoperability input-output model: a case study of the Taal Volcano eruption. *Sustain. Resil. Infrastruct.* 8 (sup1), 68–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/23789689.2022.2127999>.
- Tilloy, A., Malamud, B.D., Winter, H., Joly-Laugel, A., 2019. A review of quantification methodologies for multi-hazard interrelationships. *Earth Sci. Rev.* 196, 102881. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.earscirev.2019.102881>.
- West, J., 2023. Social vulnerability and population loss in Puerto Rico after Hurricane Maria. *Popul. Environ.* 45 (2), 8. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11111-023-00418-3>.
- Wong, S.D., Pel, A.J., Shaheen, S.A., Chorus, C.G., 2020. Fleeing from Hurricane Irma: empirical analysis of evacuation behavior using discrete choice theory. *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* 79, 102227. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2020.102227>.
- Yamada, T., Yamasaki, N., 2021. Simulation of tsunami evacuation behavior considering inland direction. *Int. J. Disaster Risk Reduct.* 65, 102566. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijdrr.2021.102566>.
- Yang, Y., Mao, L., Metcalf, S.S., 2019. Diffusion of hurricane evacuation behavior through a home-workplace social network: A spatially explicit agent-based simulation model. *Comput. Environ. Urban Syst.* 74, 13–22. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compenvurbsys.2018.11.010>.
- Zachry, B.C., Booth, W.J., Rhome, J.R., Sharon, T.M., 2015. A National View of Storm Surge Risk and Inundation. *Weather Clim. Soc.* 7 (2), 109–117. <https://doi.org/10.1175/WCAS-D-14-00049.1>.
- Zaitchik, B.F., Omumbo, J., Lowe, R., van Aalst, M., Anderson, L.O., Fischer, E., Norman, C., Robbins, J., Barciela, R., Trtanj, J., von Borries, R., Luterbacher, J., 2022. Planning for compound hazards during the COVID-19 pandemic: the role of climate information systems. *Bull. Am. Meteorol. Soc.* 103 (3), E704–E709. <https://doi.org/10.1175/BAMS-D-21-0215.1>.
- Zhao, X., Xu, Y., Lovreglio, R., Kuligowski, E., Nilsson, D., Cova, T.J., Wu, A., Yan, X., 2022. Estimating wildfire evacuation decision and departure timing using large-scale GPS data. *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* 107, 103277. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2022.103277>.
- Zhu, Y.-J., Hu, Y., Collins, J.M., 2020. Estimating road network accessibility during a hurricane evacuation: A case study of hurricane Irma in Florida. *Transp. Res. Part D: Transp. Environ.* 83, 102334. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.trd.2020.102334>.
- Zscheischler, J., Westra, S., van den Hurk, B.J.J.M., Seneviratne, S.L., Ward, P.J., Pitman, A., AghaKouchak, A., Bresch, D.N., Leonard, M., Wahl, T., Zhang, X., 2018. Future climate risk from compound events. *Nat. Clim. Chang.* 8 (6), 469–477. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41558-018-0156-3>.